

Stickables: The Future of Tags with IoT

Enabling Pervasive Internet of Things with
Smart Stickers

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1. Stickables: Enabling IoT For Everyone

Stickables are next-generation sensor tags that anyone can use to instantly give anything with network address and sensing capabilities. This is supported through either a local edge network or with standard TCP/IP networking protocol stacks managed with smartphone digital applications and other proprietary devices that act as ephemeral mesh network consolidator and relay to more sophisticated asset management and operational analytics platforms.

Imagine a sticker or sticker roll in the form factor of a printed price tag or a traditional RFID sticker (radio frequency identification) used for asset tracking in stores, offices, warehouses, and field operations management. Upgrade this into a fully embeddable or 'stickable' low powered IoT environmental sensor that has fundamental edge network connectivity, for further processing by more sophisticated devices, networks, and computing platforms; what you get are Stickables.

Stickables can be used in several ways and through several sectors like governments, homes, industrials, businesses, health, military, and others. It addresses a few key gaps in mainstream IoT that focuses on new and smart devices, appliances, existing heavy networking standards, and systems (Miller, 2015, p.16) which are generally more expensive than traditional counterparts which may continue to operate as is or may continue to be manufactured for economic reasons.

Stickables development and commercialisation can be approached in phases as aligned with well-known adoption curve. Pursuing a segment of market targeting, early innovators and adopters allow for prototype feedback loops and product refinements. In the beginning, Stickable manufacturing will serialise fixed address ranges as sequential or hashed Thing IDs that can be pre-provided to consumers. daCosta (2013, p.3) explains that IoT can be, these simpler devices that are very much "on their own" at the frontier of the network and enable basic low-fidelity sensing in everyday objects.

These are potentially more useful with bundled mobile applications through smartphones, tablets, and other smart devices which can connect with Stickables to acquire the most rudimentary point-in-time environmental sensor information either in isolation or in concert within a mesh sensor network. Another bundling opportunity is to manufacture fixed consolidator devices or base stations than have more advanced computing capabilities for data harvest within an economically defined geofence and data forwarding capabilities for further advanced data processing. From the other end of the IoT continuum, we can have a product cloud (Porter, M. & Heppelmann, J., 2014) or an IoT cloud and analytics platform which allows higher level computing capabilities from otherwise simple sensing devices and endpoints. This IoT cloud and analytics platform is use case agnostic and can be organised and customized to suit various needs and applications.

The possibilities are staggering. Governments, business, homes, industries, and environment are all potential users. To get started intelligently simply requires the right resources to achieve critical mass and scale through a creatively segmented and targeted audience. Change and innovation are not simply a matter of actions but also a way of being and a mode of mind; one which creatively pursues the challenge of evolving ourselves through our inventions and innovations (Mlodinow, 2015).

Ashton (2015), convincingly argues that the root of innovation is exactly the same as it was when our species was born: looking at something & thinking, "I can make this better."

From the dawn, the contemporary march, to the future visions for information science and technology, our inventions and innovations emerged organically or by design to derive inspiration from complex natural system (Gibson & McGuire, 1996). With non-mechanistic and organic systems teetering on the edges of chaos and creative creation, ideas and innovations are clawing its way towards this "constantly shifting battle zone between stagnation and anarchy" which is the nexus where "complex systems can be spontaneous, adaptive, and alive" (Waldrop, 1992, cited by Gibson & McGuire, 1996).

An Exploration Of The Opportunities, Challenges, And Interacting Forces Of IoT Ecosystems.

Goal: To critically understand some of the opportunities & challenges in the IoT ecosystem.
Importance: Understanding some of the fundamental aspects of the IoT ecosystem helps with better decision making and/or further studies and investigations.

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2. Rationale - An IoT As We Make Of It

Sensing is a most essential aspect of interaction whether passive or active and whether with biological systems or human-created systems. This is the first aspect that allow things to take stock of environmental stimulus (Maney, Hamm, & O'Brien, 2011, p.244-p.255).

There are inherent challenges in introducing new technologies that hopes to connect all things. In spite of its potential for good, for example, Stickables may have consequences and ethical issues surrounding privacy and environmental impact. While non-invasive, the perception of machines sensing things and surroundings may raise both founded and unfounded ethical questions. Communicating a truthful benefit that dispels concerns is crucial (Howard, 2015). Successful mass production of Stickables may also increase environmental concerns in its manufacture, use, and disposal. These may not be simple biodegradable materials.

Information and these stacks of capabilities --- from asset tagging, aggregation of data, activation through actuators, augmenting our perceptions through feedback from higher level analysis, and the possibility of an underlying artificial intelligence that transparently imparts its influence in how our world works (IoT Patterns, 2016) --- has the potential to improve our understanding and extend human capabilities.

Better does not always mean newer or larger or smarter in an isolated case. It can be argued from a product systems angle (Porter, M. & Heppelmann, J., 2014) that better may mean connectivity at the most fundamental and lightweight level (daCosta, 2013, p.6) also as well as technological and democratic innovations (Howard, 2015) that allow the most distribution and impact to society (Gosier, 2014). This is the mission of Stickables: to provide a most democratic and intuitive way of enabling essential IoT capabilities and constructs beyond the complex hype that makes it difficult to determine reality from it (Chou, 2016, p.3). Establishing this anthropological, democratic, and human perspective as we pursue digital innovations prepares it best for deriving value from information gathered, adoption success, and learning from failures (Howard, 2015).

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